

TITLE: Assessment of Inflammatory Activity in Rheumatoid Arthritis: A Comparative Study of Clinical Evaluation with Gray-Scale and Power Doppler Ultrasonography.

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To compare the clinical assessment of overall inflammatory activity in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) with gray-scale and power Doppler (PD) ultrasonography (US). **METHODS:** Ninety-four consecutive patients with RA were included. Demographic and clinical data C-reactive protein (CRP), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) levels were recorded from each patients. The presence of tenderness, swelling and a subjective swelling score from 1 to 3 were independently assessed by two rheumatologist who reached a consensus in 60 joints examined in each patient. All patients underwent an US examination by a third blinded rheumatologist, using PD. US joint effusion, synovitis and PD signal were graded from 1 to 3 in the 60 joints. Joint count and joint index for effusion, synovitis and PD signal were recorded. A 28 joint count for clinical and US parameters was calculated. Interobserver reliability of the US examination was evaluated by a fourth blinded rheumatologist. **RESULTS:** US revealed significantly more joints with effusion (mean 15.2) and synovitis (mean 14.6) than clinical examination (mean 11.5 ($p < 0.05$)). A significant correlation was found between joint count and joint index for swelling and for US effusion, synovitis and PD signal. The 28 joint count for effusion, synovitis and PD signal highly correlated with the corresponding 60 joint counts. US findings correlated better with CRP and ESR than clinical parameters. Interobserver reliability was better for US findings than for clinical assessment. **Conclusion:** We propose that for assessing joint inflammatory activity in RA, US is a sensitive bedside method complementary to clinical evaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic inflammatory disease characterized by the development of synovitis that damages cartilage, bone, ligaments and tendons. The assessment of inflammatory activity is essential in daily practice to make therapeutic decisions and to evaluate disease outcome and response to treatment (1).

Traditionally, the degree of disease activity has been evaluated by measuring subjective clinical variables, laboratory parameters and radiographic findings (2,3,4). However, clinical evaluation of joint pain and swelling have not demonstrated enough reliability (5) and conventional plain radiography depicts indirect signs of cartilage loss and bony erosions due to previous destructive synovial inflammatory activity.

High-frequency ultrasonography (US) has greatly improved musculoskeletal imaging in rheumatology (6). Several studies have demonstrated that high-frequency US is accurate for detecting joint effusion (7-16) and synovitis (7-11,15,17-19), compared with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) (10,12,14,17) and direct arthroscopic visualization (20-22). US is more sensitive and reproducible than clinical evaluation in assessing joint inflammation (23-26).

Power Doppler (PD) US is a new technique of color Doppler (CD) that improves the sensitivity to detect flow from small vessels and those of low-velocity flow at the microvascular level (27,28). PD US detects indirect signs of increased vascularization associated with soft-tissue musculoskeletal inflammatory and infectious diseases (28,29), and enthesitis in spondylarthropathies (30). PD signal highly correlates with local clinical evaluation of joint inflammatory activity in the knee, metacarpophalangeal and interphalangeal joints of patients with RA and other inflammatory arthropathies (31,32). Recent studies have shown that PD synovial vascularity highly correlates with histologic

proven knee pannus (33) and with the degree of synovial vascularization of the knee (34) and hip (35).

The aim of this study was to compare gray-scale US and PD US with clinical and biological findings in determining global inflammatory activity assessed in 60 joints of patients with RA. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first US and clinical study that has examined so many joints in each RA patient.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Ninety-four consecutive patients who fulfilled the 1987 American Rheumatism Association criteria (36). attending the outpatient rheumatologic clinic were included. Twenty patients were male and 74 women. Mean age was 57.6 years (range 23-88 years, SD 14.3) and mean disease duration was 69.3 months (range 5-280 months, SD 58.2). Patients who had suffered traumatic, septic or microcrystalline arthritis, previous joint surgery or isotopic synovectomy within the last 12 months prior to the study were excluded.

The following data were recorded from each patient: age, sex, disease duration, drugs for RA at entry, rheumatoid factor (measured by nephelometry, normal level: 0-20 UI/ml), and previous joint surgery or isotopic synovectomy. C- reactive protein (CRP) level (measured by nephelometry, normal range: 0- 0.8 mg/dl) and erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) (measured by the Westergren method, VESMATIC 60, version 2.05, Menarini Laboratory, Barcelona, Spain) were recorded from each patient's routine laboratory test performed within 1 week of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all patients prior to the clinical and US evaluation.

Clinical assessment

The clinical evaluation was performed independently and sequentially by two blinded rheumatologist. One week before the study, they spent 20 hours in performing a

consensus joint examination in RA patients (not included in the study). The following bilateral joints were assessed for tenderness and swelling: glenohumeral, acromioclavicular, sternoclavicular, elbow, wrist, metacarpophalangeal (MCP), proximal interphalangeal (PIP) of hands, knee, ankle, (tibiotalar), subtalar, mid-tarsal, metatarsophalangeal (MTP) and PIP of feet (total in 94 patients: 5,640 joints). Hip joints were assessed for tenderness and pain on passive motion. Hip swelling was indirectly considered if pain on passive motion was detected by physical examination. A subjective score from 1 to 3 was assigned for all swollen joints except for the hip (1= mild; 2 moderate; 3= marked). Immediately after physical examination, GB and FG compared their findings. If there were discrepancies regarding the presence or absence of joint tenderness and swelling or the swollen joint scores, they performed together a third examination to reach consensus. These last results were considered for comparing with US findings. Individual physical examinations were used for estimating clinical interobserver agreement for tenderness, swelling and swelling scores. Tender joint count (TJC), swollen joint count (SJC) and a 60 swollen joint index (SJI) (sum of the swelling score from each joint) were recorded from each patient.

The following clinical variables were also recorded: a global pain intensity visual analogue scale (VASP) (0-100 mm), a visual analogue scale for patient overall assessment of disease activity (VASOA) (0-100 mm), and a self-assessment spanish version of the Health Assessment Questionnaire (HAQ) (37).

US examination

All patients underwent a US examination within 30 minutes of the clinical evaluation, by a single rheumatologist experienced in US (EN) who was unaware of the clinical findings. US examination was performed with two commercially available

ultrasound real-time scanners (Logiq 400CL, General Electric Medical Systems, Korea (scanner 1), and: Logiq 700, General Electric Medical Systems, Waukesha, WI, USA (scanner 2)) using multifrequency linear array transducers, 6-13 Megaherzs (MHz) and 5-10 MHz respectively, operating at 6.6 and 5 MHz of frequency for Doppler imaging respectively, according to the manufacturer's criteria. The first 69 patients were examined with scanner 1 and the last 25 patients with scanner 2. The presence of joint effusion and synovitis was systematically evaluated by US in each of the 60 joint clinically examined. US scanning method is described in table I The presence of effusion and/or synovitis were diagnosed in each joint according to the criteria listed in Table I (7-9,12-14,21,38-40). Distances were measured using electronic calipers. Effusion and synovitis were identified and distinguished according to the following definitions. Effusion was defined as hypoechoic or anechoic compressible intra-articular material, within synovial recesses. Synovitis was defined as echogenic non-compressible intra-articular tissue, within synovial recesses. Joint effusion and synovitis were subjectively graded from 1 to 3 (1=mild; 2=moderate; 3=marked).

Synovial vascularization was assessed by PD US in each of the 60 joints. PD imaging was performed by selecting a region of interest that included the bony margins, articular space and a variable view of surrounding tissues (depending on the joint size). PD parameters were adjusted at the lowest permissible pulse repetition frequency (PRF) in order to maximize sensitivity. This setting resulted in PRF from 500 to 1,000 Hz depending on the joint scanned. Low wall filters were used. Dynamic range was 20-40 dB. Color gain was set just below the level color noise appeared underlying bone (no flow should be visualized at bony surface) This setting resulted in gains from 18 to 30 dB. An image with maximal color activity was selected for analysis. Flow was additionally

demonstrated in two planes and confirmed by pulsed-wave Doppler spectrum to exclude artifacts.

The intraarticular PD signal was subjectively graded on a semiquantitative scale from 0 to 3 (0=absence, no intraarticular flow; 1=mild: single vessel signal; 2=moderate: confluent vessels; 3=marked: vessel signals in more than half of the intraarticular area). In each patient we recorded: joint count for US effusion (USJCE), joint count for synovitis (USJCS), joint count for PD signal (USJCPD) and a 60 joint index for effusion (USJIE), synovitis (USJIS) and PD signal (USJIPD) (sum of the effusion, synovitis and PD signal scores, respectively, obtained from each joint). In addition, we calculated in each patient a 28 joint count (10 proximal interphalangeal of hands, 10 metacarpophalangeal joints, 2 wrist, 2 elbow, 2 shoulder, 2 knee joints) (41) for tenderness (TJC28), swelling (SJC28), US effusion (USJCE28), US synovitis (USJCS28) and US PD signal (USJCPD28).

Inter and intraobserver reliability of the US examination were evaluated by recording standard images of the 30 right joints from the first 22 patients evaluated with the scanner 1 and the first 22 patients examined with the scanner 2 in a digital archiving computer system. The saved images were blindly read by the same rheumatologist who performed US examination (EN) 3 months after the initial scanning and by a fourth rheumatologist (JU), trained in US. These images did not show measurements. Prior to the study, the investigators reached consensus with regard to the US scales. Some examples of US findings are shown in Figure 1.

Statistical analysis.

Chi-square test was applied for comparing qualitative variables, and Student's t test and Pearson correlation were used for continuous variables. Any p value under 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Interobserver agreement between clinical investigators and between US investigators and intraobserver US agreement were calculated using the unweighted Kappa test. The kappa value measures agreement between pairs of observers eliminating the random concordance. A Kappa value under 0.40 was considered poor, 0.40- 0.60 moderate, 0.60-0.80 good, and 0.80-1 excellent.

RESULTS

Patients' characteristics.

Rheumatoid factor (RF) was positive in 72 patients (77.7%). Therapeutic regimens included nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs in 60 patients (63.8%), corticosteroids in 56 (59.5%), methotrexate in 61 (64.8%), leflunamide in 18 (19.1%), sulfasalazine in 10 (10.6%), antimalarial in 10 (10.6%), gold salts in 9 (9.5%), infliximab in 8 (8.5%), etanercept in 4 (4.2%), ciclosporine in 2 (2.1%) and azathioprine in 2 patients (2.1%). Two patients had unilateral hip prosthesis, three patients unilateral knee prosthesis and one patient bilateral hip and knee prosthesis. All surgical procedures had been performed more than 5 years before the study.

No significant differences between patients examined with scanner 1 and 2 regarding mean age, mean duration of symptoms, mean VASP and VASOA scores, mean joint count for tenderness and swelling, mean SJI , mean HAQ score and mean ESR and CRP values were found (Table II).

All joints, including 9 prosthetic joints, could be easily assessed by US. The US examination took 20-30 minutes for each patient, including documentation.

Clinical and Ultrasonographic joint involvement.

US detected more joints with effusion and synovitis than clinical examination. Mean USJCE was 15.2 ± 9.3 , mean USJCS 14.6 ± 9.4 and mean SJC 11.5 ± 7.4 ($p=0.003$ and $p=0.01$, respectively).

Correlation between clinical, ultrasonographic and laboratory parameters

VASP highly correlated with VASOA and HAQ ($r>0.6$, $p<0.01$). HAQ, VASP and VASOA weakly correlated with ESR and CRP ($r<0.4$, $p<0.05$).

Correlations between clinical, laboratory and US parameters are shown in table III. TJC, SJC and SJI poorly correlated with HAQ, VASP and VASOA ($p<0.01$). TJC did not correlate with ESR nor CRP ($p>0.05$). SJC and SJI poorly correlated with ESR and moderately with CRP ($p<0.01$).

US joint count and index for effusion, synovitis and PD signal highly correlated with CRP ($r>0.6$, $p<0.01$). US parameters moderately correlated with ESR ($p<0.01$), weakly with VASP, VASOA ($p<0.05$) and did not correlate with HAQ ($p>0.05$). Disease duration did not correlate with any clinical, US or laboratory parameter ($p>0.05$) (data not shown).

TJC and SJC weakly correlated ($r=0.49$, $p<0.01$). TJC did not correlate with joint count for US effusion, US synovitis and PD signal ($p>0.05$). SJC correlated with US joint counts ($r=0.58$, 0.57 and 0.56 , respectively, $p<0.01$). Correlations between SJI and US index for effusion, synovitis and PD signal were better ($r=0.65$, 0.64 and 0.58 , respectively, $p<0.01$). A high correlation ($r>0.80$, $p<0.01$) was found between all the US parameters.

TJC and SJC highly correlated with TJC28 ($r=0.95$, $p<0.01$) and SJC28 ($r=0.96$, $p<0.01$) respectively. In the same way, there was a high correlation between USJCE and USJCE28 ($r=0.92$, $p<0.01$), USJCS and USJCS28 ($r=0.92$, $p<0.01$) as well as between

USJCPD and USJCPD28 ($r=0.94$, $p<0.01$). USJCE28, USJCS28 and USJCPD28 showed a similar correlations with clinical and laboratory parameters to corresponding 60 joint counts (Table III).

When considering only the 69 patients examined with scanner 1, US findings showed a similar correlation with clinical and laboratory parameters obtained in the overall group (Table IV). There was a high correlation between US parameters and CRP levels ($p<0.01$).

Clinical and ultrasonographic reliability

Clinical interobserver agreement was from poor to excellent (Table V). Overall interobserver agreement for tenderness was better than for swelling and for swelling index. There was a high level of intraobserver and interobserver agreement, from moderate to excellent, for US effusion, synovitis and PD signal (Table VI).

DISCUSSION

We found that US was clearly more sensitive than physical examination in detecting joint swelling. In addition, US findings correlated better with CRP and ESR than clinical joint swelling. In keeping with our results, other studies (42,43) have demonstrated that US detects subclinical synovitis. Since therapeutic decisions considerably depend on clinical synovitis, the undetectable synovitis may explain the continued bone damage found in patients with clinically controlled RA. In the same way, the results of Jevtic et al (44) confirmed that in joints with inflammatory active pannus detected by contrast-enhanced MRI, progression of bone-destructive changes is expected.

Hypervascularization and angiogenesis of synovial membrane are considered as primary pathogenic mechanisms responsible for invasive and joint destructive behavior of rheumatoid pannus (45-47). Dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI findings have demonstrated a

close correlation with histologic signs of knee synovial inflammation in patients with RA (48,49). However MRI is expensive, time consuming and not widely available for routine use in most countries. Recently, PD US has demonstrated a high sensitivity (88.8%) and specificity (97.9%) for the assessment of inflammatory activity in the MCP joints of patients with RA compared with dynamic contrast-enhanced MRI (50). Over MRI, US examination of all peripheral joints can be done as many times as one wishes and prosthesis or implants do not interfere with US images. Last but not least, rheumatologist can be trained to perform US, sparing the referral to radiologist that would save time and money.

US parameters correlated with clinical joint swelling, CRP and ESR, weakly correlated with VAS scales and did not correlated with clinical joint tenderness and HAQ. Previous studies comparing clinical and US assessment have also reported a stronger correlation between US and physical examination of joint swelling than between US findings and patient's perception of joint tenderness (17,26). Furthermore, Qvistgaard: et al (26) found that the degree of synovial vascularization in finger joints detected by CD correlated with ESR, and not with VAS for pain, VAS for patient overall assessment and HAQ scores in patients with RA. In fact, joint tenderness, VAS scales and HAQ scores indicate either disease activity or structural joint damage or deformity secondary to previous synovial inflammation not present when clinical evaluation is performed.

The present study evaluated 60 joints in each patient with RA while similar previous reports investigated only a small number of joints in RA patients such as knee, MCP and PIP joints (31-33). We considered that 60 joint counts represented an overall assessment of disease inflammatory activity. However, reduced joint counts for tenderness and swelling, such as the 28 joint count (41) are widely used in the evaluation of RA

inflammatory activity in daily practice and in clinical trials. Our 28-joint count for US effusion, synovitis and PD signal correlated well with the 60 joint-count. Thus, the reduced joint count could be used in US evaluation in rheumatological practice. Although effusion and synovitis can also be seen in other recesses or periarticular locations of the examined joints, we performed a simplified US investigation in order to shorten scanning duration. The proposed US evaluation of 28 joints can be performed in 15 minutes in daily practice.

Recent studies have reported validity (50) and reliability (51) of cheaper US machines for assessing of rheumatoid synovial inflammation though most reports have used expensive machines like our scanner 2 (31-35). When analysing results from scanner 1, they were comparable to overall results. Therefore, a considerably more affordable machine like scanner 1 could be used as well.

Some limitations of our study should be mentioned. The assessment of a single selected US image instead of a real-time examination of the joints performed by the second rheumatologist obviously introduces bias in the study. However, this is the standard way to record US examination in daily practice and the images for a second reading were chosen by an experienced sonographer. Our data are in accordance with Szkudlarek et al (51) who recently reported a high interobserver agreement for the identification and semiquantitative measurement of effusion, synovitis and PD signal in small joint of patients with RA. In addition, the rheumatologist obtaining the sonograms could not be completely unaware of patient's joint signs and symptoms. To avoid as much bias as possible, US examination was made in the dark.

There are a number of potential limiting factors in the use of PD. First of all, there are no examination protocols nor standard settings for PD US machines. In addition, PD US is extremely sensitive to tissue movement, especially at low PRF, that can result in

"flash" artifacts. However, we used pulsed Doppler spectra as proof of the presence of vessels when images were doubtful.

CONCLUSION

We propose that the combination of gray-scale US and PD could be used as a sensitive and reliable noninvasive and widely available bedside method complementary to standard clinical assessment for evaluating rheumatoid synovial inflammation in daily management and clinical trials. Moreover, images of the performed examinations can be kept. PD may become a cost-effective alternative to gadolinium-enhanced MRI. Longitudinal studies that correlates PD findings with long-term clinical changes and radiographic erosive joint damage in patients with RA is highly warranted.

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FIGURES

FIGURE 1. Longitudinal sonographic image of the wrist joint with moderate effusion, moderate synovitis and mild (A), moderate (B) and marked (C) color signal.

Table I. Ultrasonographic scanning of joints and criteria of effusion/ synovitis.

Glenohumeral joint. Posterior recess, transducer transversal to the humerus, shoulder in neutral position: maximum distance from the posterior labrum to the posterior infraspinatus and teres minor tendon (posterior capsule) greater than 3 millimeters (mm).

Acromioclavicular and sternoclavicular joint. Transducer longitudinally to the joint: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 3 mm .

Elbow. Longitudinally from the anterior recess with the joint in extension: maximum distance from the humeral *capitulum* or the coronoid fossa to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Wrist. Longitudinally from the dorsal aspect with the joint in neutral position: maximum distance from the bones to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm .

Metacarpophalangeal and proximal interphalangeal joints of hands. Longitudinally from the dorsal view with the joint in extension: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Hip. Anterior recess, transducer longitudinal to the femoral neck with the joint in neutral position: maximum distance from the cortical, at the middle of the concavity of the femoral neck to the joint capsule greater than 7 mm or loss of the concavity of the joint capsule.

Knee. Longitudinally from the suprapatellar recess, in a supine position, with the joint in 30° of flexion: maximum anterior-posterior diameter of the suprapatellar bursa greater than 3 mm.

Ankle. Longitudinally from the anterior recess with the joint in slight plantar flexion: maximum distance from the talar bone to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Subtalar. Longitudinally to the joint with the ankle in slight plantar flexion: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Mid-tarsal. Longitudinally from the dorsal view: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Metatarsophalangeal and proximal interphalangeal of feet. Longitudinally from the dorsal view with the joints in extension: maximum distance from the articular bony margin to the joint capsule greater than 2 mm.

Table II. Demographic, clinical and laboratory characteristics of patients evaluated with scanners 1 and 2

	Scanner 1	Scanner 2	
	n , 69	n , 25	p
Age (years)	58.1 ± 14.3	56.3 ± 14.3	n.s.
Disease duration (months)	68.3 ± 57.9	72.2 ± 60.1	n.s
Pain by 0-100 VAS (mm)	30.5 ± 26	36.3 ± 30.3	n.s
Patient's overall assessment by 0-100 VAS (mm)	38.2 ± 26.1	38.3 ± 28.6	n.s
Tender joint count	14 ± 16.1	9.8 ± 13	n.s
Swollen joint count	10.9 ± 7.8	13.2 ± 6.3	n.s
Swollen joint index	69.8 ± 9.7	72.6 ± 8.4	n.s
Health Assessment Questionnaire score (0-3)	1 ± 0.7	0.9 ± 0.7	n.s
Erythrocyte sedimentation rate (mm)	28.4 ± 19.4	25.9 ± 14.5	n.s
C reactive protein (mg/dl)	1.5 ± 1.9	1.6 ± 1.5	n.s

Results are expressed in mean plus minus standard deviation. Abbreviations: VAS, visual analogue scale; n.s., non significant.

Table III. Correlation between clinical, ultrasonographic, and laboratory parameters

	HAQ	VASP	VASOA	ESR	CRP
TJC	0.40*	0.46*	0.36*	0.12	0.08
SJC	0.44*	0.41*	0.33*	0.41*	0.51*
SJI	0.42*	0.39*	0.32*	0.45*	0.57*
TJC28	0.42*	0.48*	0.39*	0.10	0.08
SJC28	0.38*	0.35 [†]	0.29 [†]	0.39*	0.51*
USJCE	0.13	0.23 [†]	0.31*	0.50*	0.62*
USJCS	0.15	0.26 [†]	0.32*	0.50*	0.63*
USJCPD	0.12	0.18	0.23 [†]	0.45*	0.62*
USJCE28	0.16	0.25 [†]	0.32*	0.49*	0.57*
USJCS28	0.17	0.30*	0.36*	0.48*	0.60*
USJCPD28	0.16	0.25 [†]	0.29*	0.50*	0.63*
USJIE	0.12	0.23 [†]	0.31*	0.51*	0.64*
USJIS	0.15	0.27*	0.32*	0.51*	0.64*
USJIPD	0.11	0.20	0.24	0.44*	0.63*

* $p < 0.01$ [†] $p < 0.05$

HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; VASP, visual analogue scale for pain; VASOA, visual analogue scale for patient's overall assessment; CRP, C reactive protein; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; TJC, tender joint count; SJC, swollen joint count; SJI, swollen joint index; USJCE, ultrasonographic joint count for effusion; USJCS, ultrasonographic joint count for synovitis; USJCPD, ultrasonographic joint count for power Doppler signal; USJIE, ultrasonographic joint index for effusion; USJIS, ultrasonographic joint index for synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Table IV. Correlation between clinical, ultrasonographic, and laboratory parameters in patients evaluated with scanner 1.

	HAQ	VASP	VASOA	ESR	CRP
USJCE	0.29 [†]	0.36*	0.45*	0.59*	0.67*
USJCS	0.31*	0.38*	0.46*	0.59*	0.69*
USJCPD	0.34*	0.31 [†]	0.39*	0.61*	0.70*
USJIE	0.27 [†]	0.36*	0.46*	0.61*	0.71*
USJIS	0.30 [†]	0.40*	0.48*	0.61*	0.72*
USJIPD	0.31*	0.31*	0.40*	0.59*	0.74*

* $p < 0.01$

[†] $p < 0.05$

HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; VASP, visual analogue scale for pain; VASOA, visual analogue scale for patient's overall assessment; CRP, C reactive protein; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; USJCE, ultrasonographic joint count for effusion; USJCS, ultrasonographic joint count for synovitis; USJCPD, ultrasonographic joint count for power Doppler signal; USJIE, ultrasonographic joint index for effusion; USJIS, ultrasonographic joint index for synovitis; USJIPD, ultrasonographic joint index for power Doppler signal.

Table V. Clinical interobserver agreement.

	Tenderness	Swelling	Swelling index
GH	0.57 (0.53-0.61)	1.00	1.00
ACL	0.45 (0.35-0.54)	0.00	0.00
SCL	0.67 (0.67-0.67)	-0.01(-0.01-0.01)	-0.01(-0.01-0.01)
ELB	0.63 (0.61-0.65)	0.42 (0.24-0.59)	0.33 (0.13-0.52)
WRS	0.56 (0.51-0.60)	0.50 (0.39-0.60)	0.42 (0.29-0.54)
HIP	0.58 (0.56-0.60)	0.59 (0.54-0.63)	0.59 (0.54-0.63)
KN	0.68 (0.65-0.71)	0.46 (0.43-0.49)	0.37 (0.34-0.39)
TBT	0.53 (0.51-0.54)	0.39 (0.36-0.42)	0.29 (0.27-0.30)
SBT	0.38 (0.36-0.40)	0.27 (0.15-0.38)	0.27 (0.15-0.38)
TRS	0.57 (0.51-0.62)	0.24(-0.01-0.48)	0.24(-0.01-0.48)
MCP	0.61 (0.52-0.72)	0.36 (0.17-0.51)	0.30 (0.18-0.44)
PIPH	0.65 (0.50-0.80)	0.54 (0.43-0.65)	0.43 (0.30-0.55)
MTPI	0.53 (0.44-0.61)	0.14 (-0.02-0.49)	0.20 (-0.02-1.00)
PIPF	0.38 (0.26-0.48)	0.18 (0.00-1.00)	0.18 (0.00-1.00)

Results are expressed as mean kappa values and range in parenthesis. GH, glenohumeral joint; ACL, acromioclavicular joint; SCL, sternoclavicular joint; ELB, elbow joint; WRS, wrist joint; KN, knee joint; TBT, tibiotalar joint; SBT, subtalar joint; TRS, mid-tarsal joint; MCP, metacarpophalangeal joint; PIPH, proximal interphalangeal joint of hands; MTP, metatarsophalangeal joint; PIPF, proximal interphalangeal joint of feet.

Table VI. Ultrasonographic intraobserver and interobserver agreement.

Joint	Effusion		Synovitis		PD sign
	<i>intra</i>	<i>inter</i>	<i>intra</i>	<i>inter</i>	<i>intra</i>
GH	0.78	1.00	1.00	0.48	1.00
ACL	0.68	0.83	0.76	0.59	0.75
SCL	0.90	0.90	0.79	0.46	0.82
ELB	1.00	0.94	0.76	0.76	1.00
WRS	0.59	0.73	0.62	0.41	0.71
HIP	0.89	1.00	0.88	0.67	0.88
KN	1.00	0.96	0.91	0.77	0.93
TBT	0.77	0.83	0.91	0.75	1.00
SBT	0.64	0.82	1.00	1.00	1.00
TRS	0.88	0.94	0.94	0.83	0.84
MCP	0.83 (0.75-0.95)	0.81 (0.76-0.95)	0.76 (0.74-0.85)	0.75 (0.65-0.84)	0.90 (0.82-1.00)
PIPH	0.79 (0.59-0.93)	0.84 (0.66-1.00)	0.80 (0.74-0.85)	0.77 (0.48-1.00)	0.89 (0.75-1.00)
MTPI	0.86 (0.81-0.92)	0.81 (0.71-0.92)	0.81 (0.71-0.92)	0.78 (0.65-0.95)	0.90 (0.80-1.00)
PIPF	0.88 (0.74-1.00)	0.83 (0.58-1.00)	0.89 (0.65-1.00)	0.86 (0.65-1.00)	0.90 (0.74-1.00)

Results are expressed as kappa values or mean kappa plus range in parenthesis when several joints were involved.

Abbreviations: PD, power Doppler; GH, glenohumeral joint; ACL, acromioclavicular joint; SCL, sternoclavicular joint; ELB, elbow joint; WRS, wrist joint; KN, knee joint; TBT, tibiotalar joint; SBT, subtalar joint; TRS, mid-tarsal joint; MCP, metacarpophalangeal joint; PIPH, proximal interphalangeal joint of hands; MTP, metatarsophalangeal joint; PIPF, proximal interphalangeal joint of feet